

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

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Connecting EC2U Innovation Lighthouses – part 1: increasing visibility

Report

DELIVERABLE 5.3
MONTH 12

Connecting EC2U Innovation Lighthouses – part I: increasing visibility

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I. Describing the “Lighthouses of Innovation”

A. Rationale

The capacity for innovation is a prerequisite for progress. Each city and university within the EC2U community has developed its own innovation support instruments. The objective of RI4C2 Deliverable D5.3 was to bring together these stakeholders from the EC2U innovation sphere to form a sustainable network, enabling knowledge exchange within the EC2U community, and, thus, extending and diversifying the EC2U Ecosystem.

The activities D5.3-5.5 were planned according to the overall RI4C2 approach for the formation of an EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem (PEKE) (fig. 1):

- The meetings of the “Lighthouses of Innovation” were conceptualized as networking events (D5.3)
- The Lighthouses profiles on the EC2U website increased the visibility of the topic (D5.3) and the stakeholders and enabled coordinated networking and future mobilities (D 5.4)
- The joint publication “Recipes of Innovation” will be a first co-creation based on a shared goal (D 5.6).

Figure 1: Left: Integration-activity chart, picturing the development towards a Pan-European Ecosystem. Right: The proposed value of participating in the “Lighthouses of Innovation” network.

B. Defining “Lighthouses of Innovation”

To prepare the network meetings, the Work Package 5 (WP5) Board in charge of the “Innovation Sphere” internally discussed on the nature of the stakeholders as “lighthouses of innovation”. Summarizing the discussion results, “Lighthouses” can be described as

- Pathfinders
- Innovation Offices
- Creators
- Connectors/Enablers
- Success stories

The results of the live and online discussion can also be revisited on a virtual collaboration board (fig. 2 Padlet).

Figure 2: <https://padlet.com/danastrauss/f5iw3mz7gicm167o>

C. Actions and Timeline

Identification, outreach, and survey

February/March 2022: identification and outreach to the local Lighthouses of Innovation, development of a survey for the Lighthouses (general and specific part, see Annex 1)

General questions and results of survey

1. Location

Turku	1
Jena	5
Iasi	3
Salamanca	1
Pavia	1
Coimbra	8
Poitiers	7

2. Thematic Focus of Lighthouses

3. Offers/Areas of Support of Lighthouses

4. Stages of innovation in which the Lighthouses are active

The specific part of the survey asked for the individual profile, points of contact and websites of each Lighthouse.

May 2022: The information from the specific part of the survey was compiled into an executive summary and send to all representatives of the “Lighthouses of Innovation” to get an overview of all Lighthouses and prepare for the meetings.

First networking meetings

9 and 16 May 2022: Lighthouse meetings

Each 2-hour meeting was divided into three parts:

- 13:00-13:20 **Welcome** and orientation by Board
- 13:20-14:00 **Presentations** by Lighthouses (2min each, predesigned PPT slides were provided beforehand, see Annex 2)

- 14:00-15:00 **Networking** via meeting platform (Wonder) enabling deep exchange in smaller groups

Figure 3: Participants of the Lighthouses meeting on 16 May 2022

Figure 4: Deep exchange in smaller groups

Participants:

9 May 2022	16 May 2022
Adina Mocanu	Adina Mocanu
Adriana Zait	Anne-Céline Henault
Alastair Pursell	Claudia Cavadas
Catarina Cunha Santos	Costanza Baldrighi
Chabela de la Torre	Dana Strauß
Dana Strauß	David Zakoth
David Zakoth	Ede Möser
Diana Lina	Eleonore Roderfeld
Ede Möser	Hendrik Eijsberg
Elena Vasiliu	Johannes Kretschmar
Eleonore Roderfeld	Jorge Figueira
Jorge Figueira	Lenuta Alboaie
Jorge Noro	Marjo Pihlavisto

<p>José Dias Lenuta Alboaic Marjo Pihlavisto Meri Réale Nina Küssau Oliver Pänke Oscar Lorenzo Patrícia Rita Pauli Ollikka Ricardo Costa Rita Martins Santos Sebastian Händschke Thierry Ferreira</p>	<p>Nina Küssau Oscar Lorenzo Patrícia Rita Pauli Ollikka Ricardo Costa Rita Martins Romain Lefebvre</p>
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During the presentations each lighthouse drew virtual connections to the lighthouses they felt the most thematic connection to (Figure 5). This should prepare and identify potential partner for later on-site visits (mobilities D5.4).

Figure 5: Forming a network https://padlet.com/roderle/Lighthouses_Network

Subsequent activities

20 and 27 June 2022: Workshops with the representatives of the Lighthouses to prepare the Recipes of Innovation (see report on D5.5).

Moreover, a social media campaign via the EC2U channels is scheduled for fall 2022/winter 2023 to promote the online profiles and highlight the achievements of the Lighthouses of Innovation network in 2022.

II. Profiles on website

A. Placement on ec2u.eu

To enable visibility and a sustainable networking, the profiles of the Lighthouses of Innovation are prominently placed on the EC2U website: <https://ec2u.eu/lighthouses-of-innovation/>

Path: ec2u.eu → About EC2U → EC2U Ecosystem → Networks.

B. Overview page

The screenshot shows the EC2U website's overview page for 'Lighthouses of Innovation'. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for 'About EC2U', 'Students', 'Staff', 'Researchers', 'Citizens', 'Events & News', and 'Contact'. Below the menu is a search bar and a hamburger menu icon. The main banner features a lighthouse on a rocky island at night, with the text 'Lighthouses of Innovation' overlaid. Below the banner, the breadcrumb trail reads 'EC2U > Lighthouses of Innovation'. The main content area contains a paragraph describing the project: 'The **Lighthouses of Innovation** advance coordinated networking and co-creation among European innovation promoters from Coimbra, Pavia, Jena, Iasi, Turku, Poitiers, and Salamanca. This network is part of RI4C2 project "Innovation Sphere".' This is followed by another paragraph: 'To kick off the co-creation between Lighthouses, two workshops were held to discuss what it takes to be innovative and shared best practices. The workshop was organized as two virtual and interactive events in June 2022. The results will also be part of the publication "Recipes of Innovation – An EC2U Cookbook".' Below this is a video player showing a recording of a workshop titled 'RI4C2 – Recipes of Innovation recording'. The video player has a progress bar at 1:45 / 6:08. At the bottom of the page, there is a call to action: 'Learn more about each Lighthouse of Innovation:'.

Figure 6: The overview page of the Lighthouses of Innovation

Learn more about each Lighthouse of Innovation:

<p>LIChTWERKSTATT JENA OPEN PHOTONICS MAKERSPACE</p>	<p>STUDENT HUB</p>	<p>VNiVERSiDAD DSALAMANCA Project: Innovation Lab</p>
<p>FONDATION POITIERS UNIVERSITÉ ANGOULÊME - NIORT - POITIERS</p>	<p>DIGITAL INNOVATION HUB PHOTONICS</p>	<p>FRIEDRICH-SCHILLER- UNIVERSITÄT JENA Unit: Servicezentrum Forschung und Transfer</p>
<p>cnc CENTER FOR NEUROSCIENCE</p>	<p>Elivy</p>	<p>DEPUIS 1996 SP Service du Partenariat et de la</p>

Figure 7: The lower part of the overview page, with the logos as entries to the individual profile pages (mock-up)

C. Profile pages

The screenshot shows a profile page for 'Lighthouses of Innovation' with the following structure:

- Header:** A banner image of a lighthouse at sea with the title 'Lighthouses of Innovation' and a navigation breadcrumb: 'EC2U > Lighthouses of Innovation > Digital Innovation Hub Photonics (DIHP)'.
- Section: Digital Innovation Hub Photonics (DIHP)**
 - Location:** Jena
 - Description:** Accelerating technology transfer in optics and photonics through start-ups in the Optical Valley – Jena.
- Section: Focus**
 - Optics, Photonics, Biophotonics
 - Spin-offs from 5 excellent institutes in Jena
 - „From researcher to entrepreneur“
- Section: Formats**
 - Coaching of spin-offs and spin-ins
 - International idea pitch (win 6 months of research)
 - Workshops and lectures to sensitise for entrepreneurial thinking
- Section: Details**

The Digital Innovation Hub Photonics (DIHP) is an initiative to accelerate the technology transfer from five research institutes in optics and photonics through startups. At the annual DIHP-Elevator Pitch extensive research budgets can be won by already established startups or entrepreneurs-to-be.

« The biggest challenges are the different mindsets and cultures in research and business contexts. Through personal coaching we help researchers who want to found a business to develop into entrepreneurs. That's a process that takes time and patience, yet yields incredible benefits. » Sebastian Händschke
- Section: Contact**
 - Sebastian Händschke, Head
 - Eleonore Roderfeld, Staff
 - <https://www.innohub-photonics.de/>
 - Follow the DIHP on [LinkedIn](#)
- Footer:** Digital Innovation Hub Photonics logo.

Figure 8: Example of a profile page

III. Annex

A. Presentation template

Lighthouse Name

Logo

FOCUS:

- Keywords - your focus and topics

CONTACT:

Representatives, website, etc.

FORMATS:

- Keywords - your service and event formats

RI4C2
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Lighthouse Name

What we bring to the network

- Mission, competences, strong points, etc

What we hope to get from the network

- Expectations, challenges, collaboration activities, etc

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B. Executive Summary

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere

Lighthouses of Innovation

-Executive Summary-

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EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere Lighthouses of Innovation

UC Business

Description : UC Business is the Technology Transfer Office (TTO) of the University of Coimbra (Portugal). Learn more about the Special Project of the Rectory of University of Coimbra. Through the transfer of a wide range of knowledge to the benefit of Society, the mission of UC Business is to transform UC into an essential partner to the business sector, carrying out joint projects with different business structures (start-ups, spin-offs, SMEs, large companies and associations), within the multiple areas of knowledge of the University of Coimbra.

UC Business organizes its action into three pillars:

Value: Valorization of the different assets of the University of Coimbra, materials and immaterials, such as the knowledge of researchers, students and technologies.

Invest: invest on innovation in the medium and long term, strategically enhancing and valuing the Coimbra University.

Partnership: Development of solid and sustainable partnerships that strengthen the capacity of operation and presence in strategic sectors of national and international level.

Special focus : Technology transfer, innovation, entrepreneurship, Health; Climate, Energy and Mobility; Natural Resources, Agrifood and Environment; Digital, Industry and Space; Heritage, Culture and Inclusive Society; Blue Economy

Special topics and challenges : Technology transfer offers, entrepreneurship programs for researchers

Contact :

- PhD Nuno Mendonca, Project Coordinator
- PhD Patrícia Rita, Entrepreneurship Manager

<https://www.uc.pt/en/ucbusiness/>

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EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere

Lighthouses of Innovation

Lichtwerkstatt Jena – Open Photonics Makerspace

Description : The LICHTWERKSTATT JENA is a makerspace located at the Abbe Center of Photonics of the Friedrich Schiller University Jena with a focus on optics and photonics. The working space provides free access to different technologies (e.g., 3d printers, 3d scanners, laser cutters, VR/AR glasses, microcontrollers) and offers a varied program of events (e.g., workshops, hackathons). The goals of the makerspace are to support innovation and foster collaboration between scientists, industry leaders, startups and the maker community!

Special focus : Photonics, Light and Optics

Special topics and challenges : The LICHTWERKSTATT makerspace is used by scientists, students, hobbyists and startups that work on innovative ideas that are in the field of photonics. Due to our location at the Abbe Center of Photonics at the Friedrich Schiller University Jena, we can provide photonics specific mentoring. Our daily work involves a lot of rapid prototyping (e.g. with 3D-printing, laser cutting, microcontrollers) where we also work with design thinking approaches to keep the user in the center of the mostly technical solutions invented in the makerspace.

Contact :

- David Zakoth, Strategy | Marketing | Open Innovation

- Johannes Kretzschmar, Prototyping | Mentoring | Data Science
- Sabine Best, Communication | Cooperation | Events
- <https://lichtwerkstatt-jena.de/>

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere

Lighthouses of Innovation

Student Hub | University of Coimbra

Description : Student Hub aims to be an integrated circuit of services and information to improve the quality of reception and care of students, guided by an innovative model in which internal and external services are available physically and digitally: academic management services, social services, international relations and so on.

But the Student Hub also serves the purpose of diversification of skills and the enhancement of skills for students through the creation of volunteer programs, civic/territorial initiatives and collaborative initiatives aiming social innovation. Therefore a Design Thinking Laboratory and an Academy of Creators promoting activities that organize the scientific areas to respond to societal challenges are present, as well UC Transforma, a platform for volunteer offerings, and a Center for Student Employability. Generate talents, accompanying them and advising them, making their paths more flexible and connecting to different communities, institutions, entities, organizations and local businesses is also the objective of this new UC structure.

Special focus : Innovation, inclusivity and sustainability.

Special topics and challenges : Administrative modernization, connecting with the territories (schools and municipalities), talents management, promotion of soft skills.

Contact :

- José Dias, Student Hub Coordinator
- <https://www.uc.pt/studenthub/>

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere

Lighthouses of Innovation

Institute of Interdisciplinary Research

Description : We are a focused unit for third cycle and interdisciplinary research. At the University we operate as a support institute for research and development centres and researchers. We support Interdisciplinary Initiatives that bring researchers closer to innovation and research networks, such as companies, associations, among others.

Special focus : Research, Science Communication, PhD Programmes

Special topics and challenges : We deal daily with the challenge of innovating in science in order to make research more competitive and disruptive, resulting in better and higher funding

Contact :

- Dr. Rita Martins dos Santos, Project Manager
- Professor Cláudia Cavadas, Vice-Rector for Research at University of Coimbra and Director of Institute of Interdisciplinary Research
- www.uc.pt/iii

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere Lighthouses of Innovation

Fondation Poitiers Université

Description : The purpose of the Fondation Poitiers Université is to collect donations from individuals and companies, in order to finance projects led by members of the University community, whether they are students, researchers or administrative staff.

Special focus : Our foundation is committed to three axes, i) research and innovation, ii) territorial anchoring and international visibility and iii) the fight against student precariousness in a vision of sustainable and solidarity-based development. As part of the fir

Special topics and challenges : As our University is multidisciplinary, we are led to support projects in many fields, ranging from chemistry, physics, biology to human and social sciences. However, the fields in which we are most active via our research chairs are: i) educational sciences (including immersive learning), ii) brain aging and dependency-care, ii) the study and preservation of terrestrial and aquatic biodiversity, iv) cybersecurity and v) health data processing.

Contact :

- Dr. Thierry Ferreira, Director
- <https://fondation.univ-poitiers.fr/>

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere Lighthouses of Innovation

"Transfer and Valorization of Scientific Knowledge" project | University of Coimbra

Description : The UI-Transfer project "Transfer and Valorization of Scientific Knowledge" aims to increase the potential for the valorization of scientific and technological knowledge through network dynamics, enabling the viability, acceleration, and capitalization of innovative projects in the market.

Special focus : Deep tech transfer

Special topics and challenges : Good practices of technological surveillance actions; Good practices in technology transfer; Strategies for collaboration between partner institutions in the valorization of joint technologies;

Contact :

- Dr. Ana Querido, Innovation Manager
- Doctor Nuno Mendonça, Project Coordinator
- www.uc.pt/ucbusiness

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere Lighthouses of Innovation

“BiotechSTARS” project | University of Coimbra

Description : Project BiotechSTARS - project to foster and support a bio-entrepreneurship culture among investigators and other players of the biotechnology landscape.

Special focus : biotechnology, bio-entrepreneurship, valorization of healthcare technologies

Special topics and challenges :

Contact :

- PhD Catarina Cunha Santos, Head of Technology Transfer Office
- <https://cnc.uc.pt/en>

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere Lighthouses of Innovation

Innovation Services | University of Turku

Description : At university of Turku, we have several biomarker innovations yearly. To help our researchers to commercialize these innovations we have participated in the compilation of some of the best practices and pitfalls encountered (practical tool) at different phases between biomarker discovery and development, as well as patent protection and technology transfer from universities, hospitals and research organizations. This type of tool is applicable to various other fields such as drug research and development processes.

Special focus : Biomarker innovations

Special topics and challenges : Before biomarker discoveries made in research optimization can be commercially utilized in the clinical laboratory, many studies and surveys need to be completed and many questions answered.

Contact :

- Dr. Pauli Ollikka, Coordinator at Innovation Services
- Dr. Marjo Pihlavisto, Innovation manager at Innovation Services
- <https://www.utu.fi/en>
- <https://biomarker.nu>

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere Lighthouses of Innovation

Rubik Hub

Description : Rubik Hub is more than a physical place, it is an emerging community, formed of people with mutual values, a desire to grow and a common ****VISION****: live in a world where each person can reach the best version of themselves and drive positive impact.

We embarked on a brave ****MISSION****, to develop and connect communities, together with whom we inspire, educate and accelerate startups from 0 to 1 and create global successful businesses.

Special focus : Startups, innovation, tech, digital, community

Special topics and challenges : We talk a lot about innovation with our startups, because the innovation is one of the most important conditions for having succes. First condition is that their idea drive a positive impact in society, to solve a problem that wasn's solved, or to do it in a better way that others have done it. We do this, growing startups from idea to the first costumer, together with a great mentors community. Give before you get is one of our most important values. I dont know if this is innovative or not, but in a world of individualism, we really value all this mentors who inspire and help the founders to make their first steps as startups.

Contact :

- Georgiana Vieru Horosincu, Community Manager
- Robert Cotuna, Site coordinator
- <https://rubikhub.ro/>

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere Lighthouses of Innovation

Pépité Poitiers

Description : PEPITE – Student Center for Innovation, Transfer and Entrepreneurship is a National label awarded by the Ministry of Higher Education and Research.

Its objective is to raise awareness and train students and young graduates in entrepreneurial culture and to support them in their creative process. With a conception of entrepreneurship that does not only cover the creation of a activity but which is above all a state of mind, to build, to change, to innovate...

Special focus : Student entrepreneurship

Special topics and challenges : Vast diversity of innovation projects often linked to research laboratories. Promotion of these projects with our partnerd structures.

Contact :

- egu Sandra Choisy, Service manager
- Alastair Pursell, development and support
- <https://pepите.unilim.fr/>

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere Lighthouses of Innovation

Center for Technology Transfer | Alexandru Ioan Cuza University Iasi

Description : TT Entity Mission Statement

The iTransfer Technology Transfer Center (CTT-iT) has established its mission to drive the innovation and technological transfer in order to capitalize on achieved research results through implementation on the market as innovative products and services.

TT Entity Goals : CTT-iT was established in order to directly address both the requirements of the academic environment for promotional services, as well as the industry necessity for innovative solutions implementation oriented consultancy services

Special focus : Information Technology and Communications, space and security 1. Information and Communications Technologies Future Internet Software development technology, tools and methodologies 2. Infrastructure and services information security

Special topics and challenges :

Contact :

- Prof. Dr. Lenuta Alboaie, Director of CTT iTransfer
- Drd. Diana Lina, Technology Transfer Officer
- <https://itransfer.space/>

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere

Lighthouses of Innovation

R&D International Networks

Description : R&D International Networks is an Office, under therectory direct coordination to promote and disseminate opportunities for collaboration within international consortias in all fields of research and for all stages of development.

Special focus : There is a strong cluster in Coimbra on the field of Healthcare and there is a wider number of opportunities in this area.

Special topics and challenges : Education (Master and PhD, summer schools, bootcamps, etc); Business Creation (early Stage, internationalization) and Innovation Projects. Knowledge Intensive Communities involvement and participation EIT consortias).

Contact :

- Ing Jorge Figueira, Office Coordinator
<https://ucpages.uc.pt/en/rdit/>

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere Lighthouses of Innovation

Service Centre Research and Transfer | University of Jena

Description : With the Service Centre Research and Transfer (SFT), a central department for the promotion of research and transfer was created at the University of Jena. The SFT offers all members of the university wide-ranging professional support services for carrying out their diverse scientific activities. The SFT provides access to networks in science and industry and, with its service-oriented work, serves as a competent point of contact for scientists, researching institutions, innovation-oriented companies as well as decision-makers in politics, administration and associations. The SFT creates a platform for the exchange of information on the topics of research funding and transfer.

Special focus : The Research and Transfer Service Center offers support services along the entire value chain: Starting with the application for third-party funded research projects to the (technology) transfer topics of cooperation initiation, patent management and start

Special topics and challenges : Challenges: bureaucratic obstacles, legal framework conditions, lengthy coordination processes,

resource problems, search for business partners...

Strengths: Anchoring and integration of the various transfer topics from research funding, property

rights management to start-up support in a central department as a one-stop service.

Contact :

- Dr. Oliver Pänke, Head of the Transfer Service Unit at the SFT
- <https://www.uni-jena.de/en/sft>

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere

Lighthouses of Innovation

Agence Aliénor Transfert

Description : Aliénor Transfert Agency accelerates the transfer of technologies and knowledge from public research in northern Nouvelle Aquitaine to private society and other players in the socio-economic world, but also to start-up creation. Resulting from a consortium, the Agency federates seven founding establishments: the University of Poitiers and Limoges, ISAE-ENSMA, CNRS and Technopole Grand Poitiers.

Special focus : Technology maturation, transfert to socio-economic world and start-up creation

Special topics and challenges : Pre-Maturation, Maturation, Transfert

Contact :

- Dr. Romain Lefebvre, Project manager
- Cédric Lebailly, Business unit manager
- <https://www.alienor-transfert.com/>

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere Lighthouses of Innovation

"Alaturi de Voi" Romania Foundation (ADV Romania)

Description : The ADV Romania Foundation is a non-governmental organization and a social enterprise, established in February 2002 whose mission is the integration of people with disabilities or other vulnerable groups.

ADV Romania is one of the biggest social enterprises from Romania, built around the one-stop-shop principle, according to which a disadvantaged individual or someone having lived in a placement center can access a package of services addressing several issues: social and psychological services, educational services, professional orientation, qualification, employment and assistance at the workplace.

1. Experience in social economy on incubation/acceleration
 - ADV Romania owns three social enterprises, of which one is a work integration social enterprise;
 - The foundation is grant administrator for 42 social enterprises from Romania financed through the European Social Fund.
 - We are currently establishing and will finance 5 social enterprises in the Republic of Moldova and 3 in Ukraine.
 - We have established and own the presidency of the "Accelerator of Social Enterprises" cluster, registered on the European Cluster Collaboration Platform and in which are included 50 entities.
 - We have developed 2 online instruments for the social economy sector in Romania – R. Moldova - Ukraine: The Virtual Map of Social Enterprises and the Regional Observer of Social Economy. We intend to expand these instruments in the European Union as well. For further details, please access <https://accelerator.alaturidevoi.ro/>
2. Experience in VET

- ADV Romania owns a package of 6 certified trainings: Entrepreneur in Social Economy, Manager of a Social Enterprise, Project Manager, Human Resources, Archiving and Manual Book-binder.

3. Experience in research, public procurement and advocacy

- In 2021/2022 we developed 3 researches at national level and launched 1. The Barometer of Social Economy 2021; 2. The Barometer of Socially Responsible Public Procurement; 3. The Barometer of Social Financing.

- We have contributed to the passing of the Law on Social Economy in Romania in 2015 and of 5 legislative proposals meant to improve the ways in which work integration social enterprises are functioning. Two proposals were passed in 2017 and 2020 and 3 other proposals are submitted to the Romanian Parliament in 2022.

4. Experience in financial instruments.

ADV Romania is currently working to establish a non-banking financial institution for loaning social enterprises from Romania. AFIN IFN S.A. will be officially registered and will become operational in Romania in April 2022. For details, please access www.afin.org.ro Currently, 170 physical and juridical entities have become stakeholders.

Special focus : Social innovation; work integration of people from vulnerable groups and people with different disabilities; administrator of grants for social enterprises/SME's

Special topics and challenges : Challenges: financial sustainability of social enterprises in Romania; fiscal legislation to support these entities; selling products and services of social enterprises.

Others can learn:

- ADV Romania's experience in developing Social Innovation Labs for young people can be disseminated in other countries;
- The European Conference in Social Economy, at its second edition (<https://www.facebook.com/events/961484221399277>), can become an instrument useful for bringing the topic to the European public agenda and for facilitating experience exchanges;
- ADV Romania has the technical capacity to develop virtual study visits in social enterprises from Romania.

Contact :

- VASILIU Elena, Marketing and Communication Specialist

- Iftimoaei Manuela, Head of Department for European projects
www.alaturidevoi.ro

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere Lighthouses of Innovation

Ellyx

Description : Ellyx is a French firm created in a cooperative form in 2013. It is located in Poitiers, Bordeaux, Paris and Lyon. Our team is composed of 20 people, among which 8 are associates of the cooperative firm.

Special focus : Social innovation, social R&D

Special topics and challenges : We aim to face social and environmental challenges, such as education, health, employment, nutrition, ageing, etc., with answers that are deeply transformative in the benefit of the common interest. We seek to gather stakeholders into cooperation projects, in order to answer social issues. We support several actors (public, private, third sector or civil society) working on social issues in developing impactful services, activities or policies from their emergence to their implementation. To do so, we rely on social R&D to foster social innovation projects, with consulting, training, contents on social innovations or initiatives.

Contact :

- PhD Olivier Palluault, Company manager
- Meri Réale, Innovation transfer director
- www.ellyx.fr

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere Lighthouses of Innovation

Service du partenariat et de la valorisation de la recherche (SPVR)

Description : The spvr is a shared office between three research establishments (University of Poitiers, ISAE-ENSMA and the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)). The office have in charge the establishment of partnerships with academia, industry and regional authorities, the supports calls for scientific proposal and Innovation (IP, Start-up, Technology Transfert).

Special focus : Collaboration contrat, Calls for scientific proposal, Innovation, Deep tech,

Special topics and challenges : IP, Technology Transfer

Contact :

- Cédric Lebailly, Director
- <https://www.univ-poitiers.fr/decouvrir-la-recherche/ressources-pour-les-chercheurs/partenariats-valorisation-et-appels-a-projets/>

EC2U RI4C2 WP5 Innovation Sphere Lighthouses of Innovation

Innovation Lab | University of Salamanca

Description : Today, the innovation lab is an idea or concept promoted by the vice rectorate for research and transfer at the University of Salamanca. Its embryonic and does not yet have dedicated spaces or resources. It arises from the AGRIENVIRONMENT project, a strategic institutional development project for CIALE, the Institute for Agribiotechnology Research and its effort by the same name "AGRIENVIRONMENT - Innovation Lab" to build multidisciplinary "task force" groups around impact concepts that will promote the Agrienvironmental Campus in Salamanca.

Special focus : At the moment the focus is the one that started with the AGRIENVIRONMENT. Agriculture, Sustainability and the Environment. The foreseeable future would take our focus into building capabilities to support impact across the institution.

Special topics and challenges : Based on my previous experience. Today the activity in this area is still poor.

Contact :

- Ricardo Costa, Manager at AGRIENVIRONMENT

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CHU de Poitiers

Description : Public health establishment, with a mission of care, teaching and research

Special focus : Health

Special topics and challenges : Innovation in health

Contact :

- GORRY Noëlla, business development officer, lawyer

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Digital Innovation Hub Photonics (DIHP)

Description : Accelerating technology transfer in optics and photonics through start-ups. In the Optical Valley - Jena.

Special focus : Optics and Photonics Spin-offs

Special topics and challenges : The Digital Innovation Hub Photonics (DIHP) is an initiative to accelerate the technology transfer from five research institutes in optics and photonics through startups. At the annual DIHP-Elevator Pitch extensive research budgets can be won by already established startups or entrepreneurs-to-be.

The biggest challenges are the different mindsets and cultures in research and business contexts. Through personal coaching we help researchers who want to found a business to develop into entrepreneurs. That's a process that takes time and patience, yet yields incredible benefits.

Contact :

- Dr. Sebastian Händschke, Head
- Eleonore Roderfeld, Staff
- <https://www.innohub-photonics.de/>

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AIPED Pedagogical Innovation Unit

Description : AIPED Pedagogical Innovation Unit offers support to stimulate pedagogical Innovation within UC and transform its curricula and pedagogical practices; Leverage the continuous improvement of learning and teaching; Promote academic success and prevent early school drop out; Prevent academic fraud and plagiarism; Promote pedagogical Innovation and learning improvement projects and Promote inovative processes towards inclusion, literacy and tutoring

Special focus : Pedagogical Innovation towards the Higher Education community of teachers and researchers

Special topics and challenges : New and innovative approaches to teach and to learn in Higher Education institutions and organisation of initiatives to stimulate them within the community.

Contact :

- Ing. Jorge Figueira, Office Coordinator
- <https://ucpages.uc.pt/aiped/iniciativas/premio-inovacao-pedagogica/>

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International Startup Campus

Description: The International Startup Campus is an initiative of the largest universities in Jena, Halle, and Leipzig in the central German triangle of three federal states. This initiative is intended to support German startups to internationalize and international startups to settle in the region.

The areas of action are divided but still connected by three A's:

Attract - Attracting international founding teams and startups to the entrepreneurial and research hub in central Germany

Academy - Developing competencies for company growth and internationalization

Accelerate - Supporting companies entering the Asian market through hubs in China, Japan and Vietnam

Special focus: Deep Tech, technology-oriented startups and innovation, EXIST-GS/FT support, internationalization of startups, qualification of startups

Special topics and challenges: We offer international access as a university platform to build up a network of national and international experts to support founders and startups for innovation and international growth.

Contact :

- Valerie Daldrup, Coordinator
- Ede Möser, Project Manager Academy
<https://internationalstartupcampus.com>

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SPN - réSeau des Professionnels du Numérique

Description: We are a network dedicated to local digital companies. We aim at helping these companies connecting together and with the ecosystem of innovation and intrapreneurship. We build actions to help them grow, recruit, innove, ...

Special focus: Digital

Special topics and challenges: We have different acceleration programs to help entrepreneurs build their innovative digital projects, we organise some events to promote startups methods and impulse the taste of entrepreneurship.

Contact :

- Anne-Céline Henault, Projects coordinator
- <https://www.spn.asso.fr/>

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